

Introduction

With composites being used in an increasing number of high-performance applications, a strong understanding of their performance under a variety of conditions is essential. One area that has little consensus and guidance of best practice, whilst also lacking any test standards, is the testing of composite materials at intermediate, i.e., less than 100 s^{-1} (see Figure 1), (or higher) strain rates. At these strain rates, data, especially that of load, can be difficult to interpret due to the presence of load signal oscillations caused by stress waves through the specimens and inertial effect of the test system. While filtering and smoothing can be used to aid data interpretation, it is not ideal and may affect the measurement uncertainty. To provide greater confidence in collected data, methods to minimise stress waves and inertial effects on the load signal are needed. For both, the quality of data can be somewhat influenced by the choice of strain rate and test specimen geometry, though as the test speed increases so will the inertial effect on the load signal. The work presented here provides findings from an initial study looking into the influence of various geometric parameters, i.e., gauge length, gauge width, and overall specimen length, on the strain rates achievable during testing. This work is part of a broader program looking to develop best practice for testing at intermediate strain rates using hydraulic test machines.

Figure 1: Strain rate regimes with associated testing systems and dynamic considerations

Experimental Methods

Intermediate strain rate testing was undertaken using an Instron VHS 160/100-20 (Figure 2), a servo-hydraulic test machine that has a static and dynamic load capacity of 160 kN and 100 kN, respectively, with a top actuator speed of 20 m/s. In the work presented here, tensile loading was done using the Fast Jaw gripping system (Figure 3, left), which works by accelerating over the length of the specimen, gripping and loading once the actuator has reached the desired test speed through the release of knockout wedges. Due to the principle of operation of these grips, test specimens tend to be reasonably long, of the order 350 mm or greater, with their length somewhat dictated by the chosen actuator speed. Another gripping system known as a Slack Rod is also available but is currently the subject of further work.

Strain measurements were made using 3D digital image correlation (DIC) using two Photron Fastcam Nova S16 high speed cameras arranged in a stereo pair. These cameras can achieve 16,000 frames per second (fps) at a full frame resolution of 1 Megapixel (Mpx), up to 1.1 million fps at a cropped image size of 128 px × 16 px.

Figure 2: Instron VHS test machine with Photron high speed cameras

Figure 3: Fast Jaw grips (left), Slack Rod grips (right)

When testing at intermediate strain rates, the consideration of the test specimen geometry is two-fold: (1) to achieve the desired strain rate, and (2) to ensure enough strain data can be collected when using high speed cameras. As the strain rate increases, the overall test times become shorter requiring increased data acquisition rates. On VHS style hydraulic test machines, data acquisition is not usually an issue as these machines can generally acquire data at rates into the 10's of MHz if required. However, high speed cameras are generally more restricted as an increase in frame (acquisition) rate requires a cropping of the image sensor and thus a reduction in image resolution. For instance, at a strain rate of 100 s^{-1} and a camera frequency of 100 kfps, only 10 images will be captured per percent strain. For a material with 2% strain at failure, this results in the capture of only 20 images for the whole test. Additionally, cropping the image sensor to increase the frame rate reduces the field of view (Figure 4), though this can be rectified with the correct choice of lens. To circumvent these restrictions, it is suggested that test specimens have a waisted gauge area to promote failure within a particular region. This means that the area over which strain is measured in captured images can be maximised depending on the frame rate and its forced image resolution.

Figure 4: Comparison of cropped image sensor sizes

In this study, tensile testing was conducted on a Tufnol 10G/40 0/90 cross-ply glass-fibre epoxy composite. Geometric parameters (gauge length, gauge width and overall length) were individually varied while fixing all others, i.e., vary gauge length whilst fixing gauge width and overall length. Specimens were waisted with a 12 mm radius leading into the gauge area. The gauge area is offset from the centre of the specimen length, resulting in one grip length being much longer than the other; this is due to the required travel needed by the Fast Jaw grips. Figure 5 shows a schematic of a test specimen, while Table 1 shows how the parameters were varied. All tests were run with an actuator speed of 5 m/s.

Figure 5: Schematic and example of a test specimen

Table 1: Variations of specimen geometry

(mm)	Length		
	550	450	350
GL			
20	✓		✓
15		✓	
10			✓
GW			
16	✓	✓	✓
12	✓		
8	✓		

Results

The testing in this study generally shows that there is a clear influence of specimen geometry on the strain rate.

One geometric variation was to change the overall length of the test specimen from a length of 550 mm down to 350 mm, whilst keeping the gauge length and gauge width fixed at 20 mm and 16 mm, respectively. The minimum length chosen here reflects the lowest position of the machine crosshead as a result of the Fast Jaw gripping fixture. Since the actuator test speed remains constant at 5 m/s, the acceleration distance remains the same for all specimens. As such, to load shorter specimens the machine crosshead must be lowered. As shown in Figure 6, reducing the overall length results in a noticeable increase in the strain rate. This is to be expected as by reducing the overall length, the distance between gripping points, the 'effective' gauge length, is reduced and thus load uptake can be achieved much quicker. Additionally, reducing the overall length and therefore the 'effective' gauge length, the noise in the strain data also reduces.

Interestingly, by reducing the gauge length of the waisted section from 20 mm to 10 mm, and keeping the overall length and gauge width fixed at 550 mm and 16 mm, respectively, there is no change in strain rate (Figure 7). There appears to be only a minor change in the strain at failure. This lack of change likely indicates that on specimens of this length, with the exception of the promotion of failure, the gauge length of the waisted section plays little effect on the strain rate when compared to the 'effective' gauge length between the gripped points.

In contrast to the effect of waisted gauge length on strain rate, there is a clear effect of the gauge width on the strain rate. As shown in Figure 8, by reducing the gauge width from 16 mm to 8 mm, whilst maintaining an overall length of 550 mm and a gauge length of 20 mm in the waisted section, there is an increase in the strain rate. In addition, reducing the gauge width has resulted in a clear increase in the measured strain at failure. Alongside this increase in strain rate and strain at failure there does appear to be an increase in the noise of the strain data, though a clear trend through the data is still observable.

Figure 6: Effect of specimen length on strain rate

Figure 7: Effect of specimen gauge length on strain rate

Figure 8: Effect of specimen gauge width on strain rate

Conclusions

From the work conducted thus far, there is a clear effect of specimen geometry on the strain rate. Reducing the overall length shows an increase in strain rate and a reduction in noise in the strain data. A similar increase in strain rate was also observed when reducing the width of the waisted gauge section, though the strain data noise appears to increase here. In contrast, reducing the gauge length of the waisted section had no effect on the strain rate or data noise. The data suggests that while the strain rate can be influenced by the specimen geometry, there are dimensions that begin to negatively affect the output data. Here, a maximum length and minimum gauge width could be suggested to both ensure acceptable data quality whilst also ensuring the promotion of failure to a specific region.

This work is part of a broader project looking to develop good practice when testing at intermediate strain rates using a hydraulic test frame. Further work includes:

- Continued optimisation of tensile specimen geometries, for both the Fast Jaw and Slack Rod gripping systems, with the intention of providing suggestions for specimen design depending on the strain rate required
- A study to look into effective solutions to the minimisation of load train noise in order to improve the quality of the data collected during loading.
- Compression testing at intermediate rates, with an optimisation of test specimen dimensions